

Joint Workshop ERICA – c4c

“Exploring and enhancing the potential for ERN registries to advance research in rare and paediatric conditions”

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Marsilius College – Heidelberg University Hospital

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Introduction

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The workshop was co-organised and co-hosted by two European Projects with an interest in rare and paediatric disease data. The European Rare Disease Research Coordination and Support Action consortium (ERICA) and conect4children (c4c).

ERICA is a project which assists in the development of safe and easy to access therapies for the benefit of patients with rare disease. The consortium brings together all 24 European Reference Networks (ERNs). c4c is large project which aims to create better medicines for babies, children and young people through the establishment of a pan-European clinical trial network. Both projects have Work Packages (WP) dedicated to data: whereas ERICA has always had a focus on ERN registries (and delivered a first workshop in Heidelberg in late 2022), in its final years c4c has broadened its data focus from clinical trial data per se, to considering the extent to which registry data could support clinical trials in paediatric and rare diseases. Given this common focus, the leads of these WP worked across the two projects to prepare and deliver this workshop to meet shared goals, identify opportunities for learning and solve common gaps.

Goals of the workshop:

- To bring together representatives of ERN registries, c4c partners, and additional experts, to better understand the current potentiality of the existing 24 ERN's registries with respect to paediatric research and regulatory purposes.
- To discuss ERNs collaboration and communication in the post-ERICA stage.
- To identify gaps and areas which would need to be addressed to make these registries more appropriate and powerful for these activities.
- To suggest steps or actions which could be taken forward by post c4c projects to maximise the potential.

Participants at the workshop:

Who's represented?

70 registered participants, **~60** participants **on-site**

- ERN representatives & ERN-affiliated researchers → **49**
- Health Data Interoperability / RD projects → **10**
- Industry representatives → **4**
- Policy makers → **2**
- Regulatory agencies → **1**

Session 1: Status Quo of ERN Registries

Update on ERN registries - Jose Ramírez-García

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Initial feedback on registry bottlenecks and collaborations.

An overview on the operational status of ERN registries was presented. The 24 ERNs maintain registries of varying complexity and design. In several cases, individual ERNs manage more than just one patient registry. As a result, the total number of ERN-associated registries is larger than the number of ERNs (a total of 29 patient registries for the 24 ERNs). ERN registries differ considerably in terms of architecture, format, and content. Most ERNs have chosen to adopt external software platforms for their registries (e.g. Molgenis, RedCap, Castor). A minority (6 registries) opted for in-house development of their registries.

ERN registries exhibit a high degree of heterogeneity in the collection of data elements. Apart from collecting the required set of 16 Common Data Elements set by the European Platform on Rare Disease Platform, ERNs have expanded and tailored the sets of variables included in their registries to fulfil their research objectives.

ERN registries with large data dictionaries offset the associated data collection burden by defining context-specific variables (i.e., data elements which are only requested when certain conditions, such as a certain diagnosis, are met). Most ERN registries collect less than 250 data elements. Around 50% of registries include intervention and medication data, which industry and regulators find most interesting. Other registries intending to become RWE-generators should consider recording this information in the future. Registries are increasing the level of interactions with patients by allowing self-recording of PROMS through mobile apps.

An overview of centre participation in ERN registries was presented. Three categories are defined based on the level of activity and ethical approval status; active centres (those that have obtained local ethics approval and are actively enrolling patients), approved centres not yet participating (those with ethics approval but not yet enrolling patients), and contacted centres (those that have been invited but have not yet obtained ethics approval). In close to 50% of ERN registries, the proportion of active centres is larger than the other two categories. Several ERNs reiterated the administrative challenges they face in securing ethical approval, noting discrepancies in the interpretation of regulatory documents among the local ethics committees and legal departments of contacted centres. A substantial proportion of centres intended to join the ERN registries remain in the preliminary phase of obtaining the necessary approvals. Some ERN registries have chosen not to limit participation in their registries to HCPs and allow the inclusion of external centres. As a result, the reported number of active centres might be greater than the number of member centres of an ERN. While a minority, some ERN member centres have declined to participate in their respective registries. These refusals are typically driven by legal concerns or by limited resources.

ERN registries contained more than 81.000 patient records as of October 2024. Overall, the number of accessible records has considerably increased over the past years. Most ERN registries that opted for a full or combined federated approach have access to a relatively low number of records. This is largely due to federated systems often requiring additional time to develop the necessary technical

infrastructure and ensure interoperability across sites. These factors often delay patient enrolment compared to centralised models, for which the supporting infrastructure tends to be simpler.

Several ERNs have initiated projects to enable automatic data transfers from national rare disease registries. It is expected that, once implemented, these initiatives will continue to boost patient enrolment rates. This type of project however requires a significant time and resources investment, as there is not a standard universally adopted by participating countries.

Most ERN registries (28) allow data to be recorded locally by trained clinicians or research assistants in participating HCPs. Some registries (7) already allow automated data transfers to the central databases from either condition-specific registries or HCPs. 20 registries collect prospective data at either fixed or event-triggered timepoints.

Most registry coordination offices have established periodic monitoring processes to review the quality of recorded data assisted by data quality algorithms. 27 ERN registries have implemented such processes, commonly tied to Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and periodical registry performance reports (8 registries using KPIs, 20 developing them currently). 5 of these registries have already defined a frequency of 6 months for each periodic quality check, while 3 have opted to conduct them yearly. Other registries define the frequencies according to the evolution of patient enrolment rates and available resources.

Half of ERN registries have established compensation systems for participating centres. In most of these plans, participating centres receive monetary compensation per patient recorded. The exact amount of this remuneration is dependent on factors such as the number of data elements recorded, diagnosis, and, for cases where the ERN manages multiple registries, the registry in which the patient is enrolled.

ERNs have established procedures that allow the patients with entries recorded in the registries to exercise their rights (e.g., right to rectification, to erasure, etc.). In case the patients wish to modify their consent [Figure 3], 23 ERN registries allow local HCPs to directly modify the entry, while 6 registries require that participating centres contact the central coordination office. In contrast to the situation at the time of D2.5, all registries have by now defined such a procedure. Based on current experience with consent modification requests, 10 registries continue to report that any changes to a patient's consent are reflected in the registry data within one week. Meanwhile, 9 registries now indicate that such modifications take between one week and one month to become effective. The time required to implement consent changes is not always within the direct control of the ERN registry, and it often depends on the response time of the participating centres.

24 registries integrate widely used vocabularies and ontologies (apart from ORPHAcodes) within their data collection strategies. These include SNOMED, HPO, ICD-10, and the WHO ATC classification system, among others. 5 registries have been mapped to the OMOP Common Data Model. An additional 10 registries will be mapped to the CDE Semantic Model or its successor, the CARE Semantic Model.

The presentation ended with the remark that the sustained commitment and effective registry strategies of ERNs have allowed them to reach and sustain the active patient enrolment phase, as they continue to advance interoperability of their registries both between them and with other data sources in the RD research environment.

Interactive segment: Mentimeter

After the presentation, participants responded to several Mentimeter questions aimed at identifying key challenges and future directions for ERN registry collaboration.

In response to the first question regarding where ERN registries encounter the most difficulties, the majority of participants indicated that legal and ethical issues are the primary concern, with 28 respondents selecting this option. Funding and sustainability were also highlighted as significant challenges, receiving 25 votes. Technical aspects, while still relevant, were considered slightly less problematic, with 16 votes.

When asked to elaborate on specific obstacles, participants identified a lack of dedicated personnel in participating centres as the most pressing issue, which received 32 votes. Long approval processes related to data sharing and the absence of interoperability standards between EHR systems were also noted as major barriers, each receiving 25 votes. Additional concerns included unclear local legal frameworks (21 votes), inefficient data entry processes (23 votes), and the administrative burden of coordinating multiple centres (17 votes). Fewer respondents cited issues related to data quality or the absence of common technical infrastructures.

Regarding the future focus of ERN collaborations, improved data sharing and interoperability emerged as the most important priority, with 35 votes. Other areas deemed important included the exchange of knowledge and expertise (22 votes), gaining access to broader patient cohorts (17 votes), and conducting cross-ERN clinical studies (14 votes). Only two respondents indicated other, unspecified priorities.

Participants were also asked to describe their envisioned ERN collaborations using keywords that were displayed in a word cloud. Frequently mentioned terms included "interoperability", "SPIDER," "data sharing," "standardisation," "AI", and "cross-ERN studies". These responses reflect a strong interest on technical alignment and improved communication across networks. The frequent repetition of the term "interoperability" and various references to ethical and legal frameworks suggest the need to focus on harmonisation in data collection and usage.

In the post-ERICA stage, when asked what would likely be the main barriers to setting up collaborations between ERN registries, participants most often cited was limited resources, which received 29 votes. Overall, data interoperability issues were also a key concern, with 21 votes, followed closely by the administrative burden associated with collaboration (24 votes). Respondents additionally pointed to unclear governance structures (18 votes), technical challenges (10 votes), and the insufficient maturity of some registries (15 votes). A majority of participants noted that future collaborations, instead of heavily focusing on the research aspect, should first start by addressing interoperability issues and improving data-sharing capabilities. Continuing the implementation of SPIDER is also a key step.

Finally, when invited to suggest what type of support structures should take the place of ERICA, participants proposed a wide range of ideas. Suggestions included launching a follow-up initiative (ERICA 2.0), creating task forces, organising regular ERN workshops and conferences, and establishing legal and funding support mechanisms. Several comments highlighted the importance of continued coordination and the creation of dedicated projects to ensure the sustainability and scalability of ERN registries moving forward.

Session 2: Optimizing the power of ERN Registries – increasing data FAIRness and enhancing data capture features

Registry data acquisition by automated EHR extraction: holy grail or fata morgana? - Peter-Bram 't Hoen

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- EHR diversity (JARDIN survey results); existing tools for data extraction and current state of use; issues around data availability and quality; ERDERA WP9.1 activities.
- Critical appraisal of barriers, effort/benefit ratio.

Peter-Bram 't Hoen shared that both his own experience and the findings from the JARDIN survey were in agreement with the Mentimeter voting results. The major bottleneck for both ERN and non-ERN registries is their reliance on manual data entry. This process requires ongoing commitment from clinical staff, which in turn negatively impacts the long-term sustainability of these registries. While the solution is clear, its implementation remains complex. Data should be registered directly in the source systems, such as electronic health records (EHRs). Information should be recorded only once, and in a clear, unambiguous manner that would ensure interoperability and reusability. For that purpose, semantic structures and open standards should be consistently applied throughout the entire data lifecycle.

Peter-Bram and his team in JARDIN have been mapping out the landscape of registries and electronic health record (EHR) systems. There is significant variety of EHR systems in use, and even the most widely used system is found in only about 8% of hospitals. Many healthcare professionals still do not use EHRs at all. There is no single EHR system that is widely adopted across the EU, which makes harmonisation very difficult. Concerning encoding systems, ICD-10 is still the most commonly used coding system, but it is not ideal for rare disease data. HL7 is also widely used, but it does not offer the level of semantic interoperability that is needed.

Tasks within both the ERDERA and JARDIN projects are looking at ways to improve interoperability. There is currently very limited automation of data flows from health systems to registries. There are several reasons for this: not enough resources, lack of standard formats, system incompatibilities, and legal or regulatory barriers. Some actions are already underway. JARDIN Task 8.4 is testing practical solutions, and ERDERA Task 9.1 is focused on using primary care data for rare disease outcome research. These projects show that small-scale implementation is possible, but scaling this across countries and systems remains a major challenge.

Any automation still needs to be validated, which is currently done manually by clinical experts. Language is also an issue, as EHRs are usually written in the local language. One promising example from the Netherlands is the CRAMP (CRAMP: Computer Registry of All Myopathies and Polyneuropathies) solution in the neuromuscular field, which automatically extracts data from EHRs using a privacy-preserving federated approach. The pilot done with synthetic data worked well, but the challenge now is applying it to real-world data and expanding it to other countries. This will be undoubtedly much more complex.

The following project was showcased as well: <https://www.radboudumc.nl/en/news/2023/five-neuromuscular-rare-disease-registries-provide-joint-answers-to-questions-from-researchers-or-pa>

It featured 5 different registries collecting information from patients with a rare neuromuscular disease. The registries have been proven interoperable due to the adoption of common standards and the adoption of a new prototype based on a technology that connects web addresses to database queries.

To facilitate a discussion, the presenter raises several key questions:

- Will the European Health Data Space (EHDS) resolve the existing legal obstacles?
- Is structured manual data entry still necessary, or can artificial intelligence be used to extract information from clinical narratives and videos?
- Should efforts focus more on validating AI systems than on continuing manual data entry?

Discussion:

Before data can be extracted, it must first be properly collected. Language diversity across Europe complicates this further. One system developed by RDCA-DAP (Rare Disease Cures Accelerator-Data and Analytics Platform, part of the Critical Path Institute), which could serve as a model, allows for the integration of data from various countries and sources. Potential collaboration with organisations such as NORD was discussed, and uploading hospital records to shared platforms may be a useful strategy.

It was also proposed to create an inventory of existing tools, including their strengths and weaknesses. Many promising solutions are available, but they are not widely implemented in hospitals. Prioritising the adoption of these tools remains a significant challenge, and the community must make collective decisions about where to focus efforts.

While the European Health Data Space (EHDS) provides a legal framework for data sharing, it currently lacks usable implementation tools. There is however hope that this will change in the near future. The rare disease community has specific needs that require tailored approaches to data collection and reuse. It remains uncertain how quickly the EHDS will address both legal and structural barriers. Concerns were raised about whether the EHDS is fit for purpose for rare diseases and paediatric care. There was also discussion about potential obstacles arising from ongoing agreements or negotiations between EU member states, though the details of these were unclear.

The EHDS framework supports access to data at the national level but does not ensure harmonised practices around consent and pseudonymisation. A proposed solution is to establish national data hubs, allowing hospitals to sign a single agreement. Another suggestion was that hospitals should contribute to national registries, helping to link data more efficiently and reduce the administrative burden of multiple contracts.

The need to collect a minimal dataset for each patient seen within ERNs was emphasised. This requires structured forms or systems, as well as sufficient personnel and resources. There must also be consensus on which data elements should be collected and for which specific purposes. While minimal datasets can support epidemiological research (e.g. determine where patients are located), more detailed data collection is needed to answer specific research questions.

Why (and How) to be FAIR: ERDERA solutions – Ronald Cornet

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- Use of ERDERA Virtual Platform by ERN registries (Review of current state of development, onboarding of registries, potential use for inter-ERN collaborations).

ERDERA aims to bring together the strengths of academia, industry, and healthcare to make diagnosis faster, treatments more accessible, and overall improve the quality of life of people living with rare diseases. Ronald outlined several opportunities that the ERDERA project can offer to the rare disease community, including Joint Transnational Calls, networking support schemes, and other collaborative mechanisms. He provided a clear overview of the planned activities within the Data Services work packages over the coming years. An overview of the different partners involved in ERDERA and its structure.

ERDERA WP13 will focus on the development of the Rare Disease Virtual Platform and the onboarding of new users and data sources. WP15 is dedicated to the implementation of a data analysis platform. In parallel, WP16 will work on integrating data and knowledge, moving from a distributed model to a federated approach.

A key priority is to support data exchange with the Virtual Platform, even when the data is not hosted directly within it. The focus is on facilitating the connection of distributed datasets while gradually moving towards a more federated model. This direction is supported by the results of the Mentimeter voting, which demonstrated strong support for this approach (increased interoperability, data-sharing). Ronald emphasised that progress in this area will require joint efforts across multiple projects. He also gave a live demonstration of the Virtual Platform, highlighting its current capabilities and potential uses.

Although many of the processes are still being shaped, it will be important to determine how ERDERA can best support users in areas such as onboarding and the development of data management plans. Establishing these processes will be essential for ensuring that the platform can be used effectively and sustainably.

Ronald reiterated the need for the European Health Data Space (EHDS) to provide concrete support for rare and paediatric diseases. One important question is which data standards and structures will be most appropriate for connecting the Virtual Platform to the EHDS. For the sharing and linking of primary use data, the leading options are currently the EHDS record exchange format and HL7 FHIR. In the case of secondary use for research purposes, the path forward is less certain. Access to such data will likely require case-by-case negotiation with data holders, and practical solutions for enabling such access will be needed. A dedicated research infrastructure that facilitates federated data sharing must also be developed and clearly addressed within the EHDS regulations.

At present, the Virtual Platform is not formally recognised as a hub within the EHDS. However, there are metadata descriptors at the level of individual Member States that are compatible with the metadata models used by the Virtual Platform. The most effective long-term solution would be for the Virtual Platform to serve as a hub for European Reference Network registries. Alternatively, the Joint Research Centre could adopt the same metadata standards and establish a connection to the EHDS.

In practical terms, data access requests from third parties would need to be submitted to a national data access authority. Registries within that country would then be responsible for handling the request. For example, in the case of the ERKNet registry, a research question submitted through the

EHDS would go to the Federal Institute for Drugs and Medical Devices in Germany for approval. This would apply even if the registry contained data from other European Union countries. This scenario appears to depend on whether the registry in question is designated as a hub within the EHDS.

IDEA4RC, an intelligent data ecosystem for rare cancers – Annalisa Trama

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IDEA4RC aims to ensure that all observational data for adult patients with rare cancers across Europe is made available to support research, innovation, and clinical decision making. It is intended that this will be achieved without placing any additional data recording burden on clinicians. A core part of the project vision is the creation of a simple and transparent mechanism that allows data to be made accessible to all relevant stakeholders, while safeguarding individual privacy and ensuring that data providers retain full autonomy and control over their data.

A predecessor project, Blueberry, focused on data linkage using the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) Common Data Model. A key objective was to reduce the need for extensive human resources by leveraging software and automation. One of the primary challenges has been dealing with unstructured data within electronic health records. To address this, the team employed artificial intelligence and natural language processing techniques to extract information, harmonising it with both the OMOP Common Data Model and HL7 FHIR standards.

The development and use of a minimum dataset proved to be a crucial step in this process. However, when the team attempted to represent their minimum dataset within the OMOP framework, they discovered that the model did not fully meet the specific requirements of oncology data and the level of standardisation they had initially expected. To overcome these deficiencies, they developed the IDEA4RC model.

The harmonisation work and the minimum dataset have served as the foundation to develop a common data model, the NLP model, which will output structured data for the IDEA4RC project. The IDEA4RC SPE also employs the concept of a "Zero Trust" model for data access, operating on the principle of trusting no party by default.

It is intended to bring together technical experts in a webinar to further explore these developments. The project introduced a multi-layered process for data users, involving the discovery of variables, access request procedures, and dedicated analysis spaces. A user interface has been developed to connect users to the Raven platform, providing information on variable availability and data quality. Once suitable data is identified, users must follow a structured request process. To facilitate this, the team has created a data access application that compiles all the necessary information for healthcare providers to evaluate the request and then decide whether to grant access. The system as a whole operates through federated access.

This infrastructure is already operational. The team is conducting data analyses and is currently in the third year of the project. They have begun implementing natural language processing, which is showing promising results. The technology is currently being tested in four of the eleven participating hospitals, focusing on extracting information from free-text entries. Clinicians are actively annotating these texts, allowing the algorithms to be trained on custom data. Early experiences suggest that the approach is working well.

Discussion:

The project is dealing with multiple languages. At present, natural language processing is being applied in Polish and Italian, with Spanish and Swedish to follow. It was noted that this initiative could serve as a valuable model for other registries. A representative from Jardin confirmed that the team would attend the upcoming webinar.

There was discussion around whether hospitals would be able to install the necessary modules to enable data federation. This process involves navigating legal and cyber security concerns, as hospitals are often highly risk averse. Cyber security in particular has been identified as the most significant obstacle. The project team has prepared extensive documentation to reassure hospitals that the system does not increase security risks. However, responses vary: some hospital staff understand the technical details, while others grasp the broader concept of data federation. This variation in expertise makes deployment particularly complex.

ORPHAcoding still undiagnosed patients after full investigation – Ana Rath

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This presentation included recommendations on how health systems and registries should deal with undiagnosed patients. Current coding systems such as ICD-10 and ICD-11 are insufficient for rare diseases, as many rare diseases do not have dedicated codes. While SNOMED CT performs better, approximately 7 percent of rare diseases still lack a code, and many existing codes lack the necessary specificity. In recent years, extensive efforts have been made to support the implementation of ORPHA nomenclature in health information systems (HIS) such as electronic health records and/or registries so as to allow coding of rare diseases. For example, the RD-Code project, which concluded in 2022, aimed to pilot the implementation of ORPHAcodes in four countries using different implementation models. As part of this effort, a multistakeholder group was established to develop strategies for making undiagnosed patients visible within health systems.

They explored the full diagnostic pathway, beginning from the first signs and symptoms. For many patients, this pathway ends in a diagnosis. However, for others, the process stalls, and a rare disease may be suspected without reaching a definitive diagnosis, what the group defined as a "diagnostic dead end." These patients were subsequently classified as undiagnosed. In other cases, where a mutation has been identified but its clinical significance is unclear, patients are also classified as undiagnosed. However, and until recently, the ORPHAcodes nomenclature only encompassed codes for specific RD. Persons suspected to have a RD who could not be diagnosed even after full investigation, could not be coded with ORPHAcodes.

With the intention to overcome this insufficiency, the group promoted the creation of a new ORPHAcodes, ORPHA 616874, specifically for undiagnosed patients. This allows for the aggregation of such patients into a clearly defined cohort and provides a way to code them unambiguously. The group also established a definition of an undiagnosed patient, based on the World Health Organization's definition of disease. It includes patients for whom no clinically confirmed disorder can be identified by a recognised rare disease expert centre, despite the application of all available diagnostic tools and approaches.

The new code has been included in the ORPHAnet classification system at the disorder level. Although it does not represent a single disease, it offers a practical solution for grouping undiagnosed cases. The

code comes with clear guidance for appropriate use. It should not be used where another ORPHAcodes is applicable or for patients who are still undergoing standard diagnostic evaluations. Its use requires a certain degree of clinical expertise, and therefore it is recommended that only expert rare disease centres apply this code to ensure accuracy. Additionally, the code must not be used for diseases that are not yet available in the Orphanet classification, or for patients that have not reached the end of their diagnostic pathway.

The code is intended to complement the Joint Research Centre's Common Data Elements for diagnosis, specifically item 6.3. Importantly, it was highlighted that the code is considered socially empowering for patients, as it provides them with a recognised label. This recognition allows patients to enter research pathways and may also help in systems where reimbursement of care is linked to assigning an ORPHAcodes.

Discussion:

There was some back-and-forth about whether the code should be restricted to genetic disorders or not. It was clarified that the code is not limited in this way, as many rare disease patients do not have an identifiable genetic cause. The code applies to any situation where a diagnostic centre has exhausted all available tools, and no diagnosis can be given using an existing Orphacodes or through the creation of a new one. As the same genetic variant can have a range of phenotypic expressions, this code is not restricted to known molecular pathologies. When the diagnostic process has been fully exhausted, the patient is assigned to the undiagnosed cohort to allow for more advanced evaluation.

The Orphacodes is disease-agnostic and intended to be applied once local diagnostic pathways have been completed without success. This complements related work within the JARDIN project on undiagnosed disease programmes and broader care infrastructures. Assigning the undiagnosed code is expected to flag patients for more advanced, international diagnostic initiatives.

It was noted that while the establishment of a single ORPHAcodes for undiagnosed patients is a significant step forward, it may also represent a missed opportunity. There was discussion about the potential value of subcodes to indicate the primary system affected (such as liver or lung). However, it was explained that in practice, ORPHAcodes and ORPHAgroups are often assigned based on diverse phenotypes. While not perfect, as it limits the potential for stratifying undiagnosed patients into more specific categories, the single-code approach was seen as the most practical and precise solution for the time being.

SAMS: a ready-to-integrate symptom annotation tool – Dominik Seelow

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Dominik Seelow, from Charité Berlin presented a new web-based tool that could be of interest for integration with ERN registries. The tool has been designed to be as user-friendly as possible, with a web interface that avoids the need for complex installation or maintenance.

The focus of the tool is deep phenotyping, which is essential as many current health information systems primarily capture data for billing purposes. This often makes data mining extremely difficult, as it would require reading through all discharge letters manually to extract relevant information.

The tool, SAMS (Symptom Annotation Made Simple), starts with Orphanet and uses the Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO) to allow users to add detailed clinical signs and symptoms. The data can

then either be saved to a database or exported in the Phenopacket format, making it compatible with international standards.

Based on the HPO terms entered, the system can suggest a possible diagnosis and even display candidate genes. It also allows users to define their own disease groups. Integration with registries is possible either via a simple hyperlink or by embedding it as an inline frame.

It was noted that SAMS is particularly valuable because it integrates with both ORDO (the Orphanet Rare Disease Ontology) and Phenopackets, which is not always the case with similar tools. Further discussions on how SAMS could be integrated into existing databases and support deep phenotyping within ERN registries are planned.

Currently, the system is available only in English. However, it is designed to be language-agnostic, and translations of the interface are expected in the near future. SAMS can also be integrated into hospital information systems to provide preselected lists of phenotypic terms, offering a structured way to enhance the quality and granularity of data collected in rare disease registries.

Examples of the tool in action are available on the project's website, and further discussions about implementation pathways are ongoing.

The mobile registry: reaching out to patients – Mar Mañú Pereira

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- App solutions: Direct patient access to registry data, PROM data capture.

The presentation provided a conceptual overview on the development of mobile registries, which aim to improve patient engagement (although this remains a significant challenge). A brief description of the European Health Data Space (EHDS), which will address both primary and secondary use of health data, was provided. One of the main difficulties for both EHDS and mobile registries lies in the lack of structure in most electronic health record (EHR) data, which makes it hard to make this information accessible to patients. ERNs, however, could play a key role in facilitating the structuring of this data and in capturing real-world data (RWD).

It was noted that most RWD could be collected through registries, using EHR data, reported data, and research data as sources. Insights from the EURORDIS Rare Barometer surveys show that the vast majority of patients are generally willing to share their data and are keen to learn more about their condition. They also want to understand how their data is being used and be informed about the results.

Regarding preferred methods for receiving feedback on the use of their data, patients indicated a range of preferences including email, face-to-face meetings, websites, and conferences. Interestingly, only around half said they would opt to receive updates via a mobile app. This is an important consideration, given the increasing use of mobile apps in healthcare. Many patients are still not familiar or comfortable with these digital tools.

Findings from the Rare Barometer surveys were used to develop recommendations for engaging patients in registries and in the collection of patient-reported data. One of the key points identified by the surveys is the need for strong and appropriate laws that protect patients and make sure their data is handled in a responsible way. Alongside this, systems need to have solid standards and proper

safeguards in place to keep personal health information secure. It is also important to involve trusted people in shaping how data is used. This includes representatives from patient organisations who can make sure that the approach taken reflects the needs and concerns of patients.

Another message from the surveys is that systems should be able to change and improve over time. They should not be fixed in one way of working. For this to happen, there needs to be proper funding available. Some of this funding should go towards creating useful educational resources for professionals, and some should be used to inform patients clearly about what is happening with their data. Patients want to understand how their data is used and what it means for their care. They also want to know what the outcomes of research are. Finally, when people are asked to share their data, it is important to explain the potential health benefits. Knowing that their contribution could help others or lead to better treatments can make a real difference in how people feel about taking part.

One of the key challenges identified is the lack of validated tools for patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs). Fewer than 4% of rare diseases currently have a validated PROM specific to their condition. To address this, over 1,000 tools were mapped. While some are general, such as those focusing on quality of life, others are rare disease specific. A dynamic repository has also been developed, featuring a feedback mechanism for ERNs, and is open for contributions to ensure it continues to evolve.

Mobile health applications and connected medical devices offer promising tools for capturing patient-reported data, including patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs), health and treatment forms, quality of life indicators, and socio-economic information. These technologies allow patients to actively report symptoms, treatment adherence, and daily health metrics, contributing to more personalised and responsive care. Integrating this type of data into registries and electronic health records enables real-time monitoring and can support more informed clinical decision-making. The structured collection of patient-reported data facilitates the overall understanding of patient experiences and outcomes.

Close collaboration with Patient Associations remains essential for sustaining long-term engagement. These partnerships help ensure that data collection tools are relevant and accessible, and that patients remain active participants in their healthcare.

An initiative led by Ana Rath has led to a clustering of rare diseases according to their functional impact rather than by diagnosis. This allows outcome tools to be repurposed more effectively. This work will continue in ERDERA, through the Patient-Centred Outcomes Measures (PCOMs) repository.

Work Package 10 of ERDERA is dedicated to patient-centred research, with a specific focus on developing new tools for patient-reported outcomes. Task 10.2 concentrates on supporting specific networks and will focus on developing tailored COA tools for several ERNs, (EURO-NMD, RND, ERK-NET and EuroBloodNet).

Session 3: Introducing conect4children (c4c) and its data standards work, and key projects working towards the realisation of the EHDS

Overview of the c4c project and its future as c4c Stichting (Mark Turner)

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Mark Turner, CEO of c4c-S, presented an overview of the delays and additional costs that are often associated with paediatric clinical trials. He described how the services and resources developed by the conect4children (c4c) project and sustained by the c4c Stichting (c4c-S) aim to address these challenges.

c4c-S will continue the expert advice service started under the c4c project, consisting of twenty-five expert groups with over 450 experts to provide advice about paediatric clinical research. Experts sign master consultancy agreements in advance so advice can be provided more quickly, and advice is coordinated via a single point of contact (SPoC). Requests flow through the SPoC to an advisory board made up of experts in innovative methodology, clinical experts and experts in PPI, including the voices of young people. A report from the expert group is available within three months.

The SPoC also coordinates requests for site identification and feasibility and ongoing trial support, with over 250 sites in 20 National Hubs. Master Service Agreements are executed between c4c-S and each sponsor for Stichting services. Each sponsor enters into clinical trial agreements with each site for trial conduct. All sites use CDA templates for feasibility.

The c4c training platform hosts education from trainers from academia and pharma with oversight from the Secretariat and Education Board. Training modules from the project will be transferred into c4c-S.

c4c also carried out work to create resources and collaborations to support the standardisation and harmonisation of paediatric clinical trial data. This work was centred on the FAIR principles and included the creation of a Cross Cutting Paediatric Data Dictionary (CCPDD) that was developed into the [CDISC Pediatrics User Guide](#) (PUG), following the CDISC standards development process. There have been 23 contracts and 4 grants in the first 6 months of c4c-S. c4c-S is keen to work with the ERNS and can support with study design and study conduct and has experience working with industry.

Discussion:

A question was asked about how to make patients in small countries more acceptable for trials. Unfortunately, it costs the same to open a trial in a small country as it does in a large country and companies are driven by these considerations, however the quality of the sites is important. It may also be possible for countries to come together, as is the case in Scandinavia. It is difficult to influence the way companies operate, but we can listen to what they say about speed and data quality to make all countries equally attractive. c4c-S could potentially work as a broker. The emphasis on data quality is important, and ERNs are already doing this well. The more this can be showcased, the more trials can be driven through them, with access open to all patients who want to participate in trials.

Making paediatric data reuse possible-the c4c journey (Rebecca Leary, Victoria Hedley, Claudia Pansieri)

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Rebecca Leary, Victoria Hedley and Claudia Pansieri presented the data harmonisation and standardisation tasks carried out during the c4c project.

Paediatric clinical trials fail often through poor design. Having access to structured and standardised data can solve this problem. Data about children is often siloed, not standardised and not interoperable and clinical trial data about children is therefore difficult to find and reuse.

Data standards provide structure and meaning to data. They allow for easier data reuse, interoperability and data sharing. They also facilitate adherence to FAIR data principles. CDISC (Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium) was recognised as a key player for clinical research at the start of the c4c project.

A survey was distributed to all 24 ERNS in April 2021 to explore the knowledge and use of the NCI EVS (National Cancer Institute Enterprise Vocabulary Services, HPO (Human Phenotype Ontology) and CDISC within the c4c and ERN communities. The survey also sought to evaluate their potential usefulness for paediatrics and to support future planning. Ninety-two responses were received. The survey showed that as anticipated, participants had a limited understanding of these resources and provided good evidence that education and recommendations about controlled terminology would be beneficial.

At the start of the c4c project, the Cross Cutting Paediatric Data Dictionary (CCPDD) was developed to collect cross cutting items common to all paediatric studies, and it was used by the c4c Proof of Viability (PoV) studies.

The CCPDD was developed into the [CDISC Pediatrics User Guide](#) (PUG) following the CDISC standards development process. c4c and CDISC volunteers met weekly for 26 months to discuss the details of each data item – each had to be collected in trials, not clinical practice. Some of the data items already existed within CDISC but new standards were also developed. The PUG includes advice on how to structure data and implementation examples. Paediatric-specific Questionnaires, Ratings and Scales (QRS) are also included in the user guide. The PUG will result in a more standardised pool of paediatric data. Becca Leary was also involved in the development of the CDISC Therapeutic Area User Guide for Rare Diseases.

c4c collaborated with FAIRPlus to develop the recipe '[Creating a metadata profile for clinical trial protocols](#)' in the FAIR Cookbook. The recipe provides guidance for making clinical trial metadata more findable, increasing the potential for data to be shared and reused. This potentially decreases the number of patients needed for new clinical trials. It also improves the FAIRness of trial data and the potential for interoperable data sharing and (metadata-level) querying from different studies.

All of the resources created under the c4c data harmonisation and standardisation tasks contribute to the creation of a growing pool of standardised and interoperable data. They also highlight the importance of implementing the FAIR principles at an early stage of drug development and raise awareness of the need to harmonise, reuse and share data. The work carried out within the project has also challenged policy makers to consider paediatric data specificity and highlighted the importance of future-proofing paediatric data for innovation. All resources have been published so they can be widely shared.

c4c hosted a workshop in May 2022 to work on standardising disease-specific CRF data which highlighted RWD and RWE, particularly ERN registries.

A proof-of-concept study also explored how 'ready' Electronic Health Records (EHRs) are to support clinical trials and determined that they are not yet ready! This study was reported as a c4c Deliverable and published as an [academic paper](#).

c4c also hosted a workshop in February 2024 to consider whether the European Health Data Space (EHDS) is relevant for paediatric data. The consensus was that paediatric data has not been sufficiently considered in the development of the EHDS. There were two outputs from the workshop, a [White Paper](#) and an [Editorial](#).

Discussion:

A question was asked about how well CDISC standards map with OMOP. FHIR to CDISC mapping has been carried out but not sure about OMOP. CDISC standards are more granular than OMOP and FHIR. There was a suggestion that CDISC codes are not essential for use within a registry; CDISC standards are designed for use in clinical trials.

It is difficult to pick paediatric specific items from FHIR, some essential data items were found but others were lacking, however an attendee commented it was fairly easy to map the registry to OMOP. There was an additional comment that CDISC is a study-oriented data model which is different from observational models. Clinic patients are not part of a study, so it is not possible to use CDISC for everything. Mapping exercises are essential as they avoid double data entry.

How will the EHDS and its various tools impact ERN registries? (David Asturiol, Henrique Martins)

David Asturiol, DG SANTE presented ERN registries and EHDS.

[View Slides](#)

The European Health Data Space (EHDS) was adopted in January 2025 and comes into force in March 2025. It will be applied in a staggered way and webinars and FAQs explaining the EHDS will be available in the coming months. The EHDS consists of use of data for the delivery of healthcare (primary use), use of data for research and public interest purposes (secondary use) and requirements for EHR systems. The focus of this presentation was on secondary use and registries.

The EHDS establishes common European rules on who has to make data available, which data have to be made available and for which purposes and under which conditions, with a common procedure to access data. The EHDS establishes obligations for Health Data Access bodies, data holders and data users and establishes an EU IT infrastructure to share data (HealthData@EU). It also creates a streamlined process and safeguards for privacy of data subjects. Citizens can opt out from their data being used at all for secondary use and this is reversible.

The EU Central portal is a federated dataset catalogue that allows all data in Europe to be searched and found. Researchers can apply to access data with a single application. No consent is needed to

access data via the EHDS as it provides a robust procedure and safeguards that are equivalent to consent. Data is placed in a secure processing environment and cannot be downloaded. Committees inside the health data access bodies make decisions about access requests and everything is subject to transparency and is published, including fees and penalties, as well as results. Processing of data is based on public interest processing and there are clear timelines to access the data – 9 months maximum after application.

The top layer of the EHDS is a Board nominated by Member States. Below that are two steering groups – for primary and secondary use. Below that, stakeholder forums provide their input and are consulted on governance of the EHDS.

Within the EHDS, a researcher will search for what health data exists to support their research. They will request use of the data for their research project via a permit application. Health data holders and the Health Data Access Body issue the permit and make the data ready for use, ensuring data quality and privacy and provide access to the secure processing environment. The researcher analyses and processes the data and publishes results, ensuring privacy and verifiability.

Under the EHDS, the population of registries (how data gets in there) will not change at all. The EHDS changes how data is shared, not how it is collected.

Within the EHDS, registry datasets (metadata) are described, and data holders will be obliged to provide datasets to Data Access Bodies. ERN registries are by law, data holders. The HDAB publishes the metadata in a metadata catalogue to allow researchers to search for data. The researcher applies for access and their application is evaluated. Researchers are charged a fee to cover the cost of the process and the registry, as a data holder, receives part of the fee. After a positive decision, a permit is given, and the registry's data holder is asked for the data. They have 2 months to send the data to a secure environment. The data will then be anonymised, if this has not already been done and is linked to other datasets – removing people who have opted out from secondary use. The data is placed in the secure processing environment and the researcher processes the data. Once the researcher has finished their analysis, they must make the results public.

Other options are for the registry to become a trusted data holder. The registry would undergo assessment by an HDAB and have the necessary expertise to assess applications. They would carry out evaluations for data access applications (although decisions would still be taken by the HDAB) and they would provide a secure processing environment. The registry can also become a cross-border registry where the registry would self-designate a coordinator, describe the datasets and provide datasets to the HDAB in the country of the coordinator.

ERN registries can also continue to keep working as they are, outside of the EHDS, with two systems working in parallel.

Henrique Martins, xPanDH and xSHARE then also presented on how the EHDS and its various tools will impact ERN registries.

[View Slides](#)

The video '[What is the European Electronic Health Record Exchange Format \(EEHRxF\)?](#)' explores how the EEHRxF enables the seamless exchange of health information across borders, empowering patients by giving them better access to their personal health data. The initiative also enhances the security

and privacy of health information, making healthcare systems across Europe more interoperable and efficient.

Within the EHDS, the EEHRxF falls within Articles 5 n.1 priority categories of personal electronic health data for primary use and Article 6 European electronic health record exchange format.

Health is the first common EU data space. There are many silos and complexities within health, and it is important to consider how data can be shared across these spaces.

Harmonising data categories helps to create better repositories of data at the local level that can be used to feed registries. Henrique urged everyone to engage here and to understand this because hospital EHRs will have to change and it is possible to influence these changes.

Henrique included a slide showing the rights of natural persons in primary use. The priority categories for primary use are patient summaries, electronic prescriptions, electronic dispensations, medical imaging (studies and reports), medical test results (laboratory, other diagnostics, related reports), and discharge reports. Full implementation of the rights of natural persons shall be ensured. Additional data categories *may* be defined by MS. When defined, all rights of natural persons *shall* be implemented at national level in respect to these. Support *may* be included in the European format. *May* be exchanged through MyHealth@EU (where supported). MyHealth@EU is the existing infrastructure that connects healthcare providers in 14 MS.

The current live services within MyHealth@EU are patient summaries and ePrescription and eDispensation. The next service for cross-border exchange is lab results, and many registries have lab datasets. The EEHRxF is powerful tool that is also important for data harmonisation. XSHARE has a work package looking at how the EEHRxF can help clinical trials, so this is a key place to advance paediatric needs in the EHDS.

In 2014, the Rare Disease Person's Card was implemented in Portugal – a digital card available as an app and online. This was a small database at a national level and there is now a lot of data. Rare Disease and eHealth initiatives converged in Xe-Health with a refined patient summary for Rare Diseases and influenced the eHealth network which is being replaced by the EHDS Board.

In summary, the EHDS and its various tools will impact ERN registries from the perspective of primary use with better integrated data, definition of data elements for discharge notes, exploring access to and correction of data, use of automated extracts from EHRs into ERN registries, and a possible link between EHRs and CPMS. The EHDS will impact from the perspective of secondary use by exploring data sets and integrating analytics. The ERNs and especially hospitals need to engage more and more productively in interoperability and EHDS related projects. The presentation gave some examples, such as i2X, XiA, xSHARE, Xt-EHR and THEDAS2 JAs and working on MoUs between communities.

Discussion:

In response to a question about plans to support ERN registries, attendees were encouraged to reach out to Henrique Martins or Vicki Hedley to learn more about XNet organic networks.

David assured attendees that the changes are going to happen. Several projects are creating communication and training materials and there are grants for Member States to adopt the changes. The main duty for registries will be to describe their datasets and there will be tools to automate this. It will be the job of the MS to locate data holders (from 2027) and start the process. There is a Joint Action to define the technical specs of the EHDS for Secondary Use. There is an open public

consultation on some of the guidelines and comments can be added. A standard will be used to describe datasets, and this can be influenced now.

In response to a question about whether metadata from ERN registries meets the specification as it is in the JRC, it was noted that it may not be well enough annotated for what will be required, and it may not be DCAT compliant.

Most registries are well established with data access committees. Is it acceptable to carry on with business as usual in the future? It is mandated by law to follow the EHDS, but registries can keep doing what they are doing now in parallel.

Could trusted data holders be exercised by current data access committees in ERNs? The Member States will appoint the data holder to become a trusted data holder so the ERN can't decide this, it's the Member States that appoints. Another possibility is a committee that assesses applications – If they have an agreement with these committees for evaluating proposals on Rare Diseases. This is a possibility, but Member States will decide how they will do this.

It was noted that a FAQ for registries is needed.

A question was posed about how patients are empowered to be in control of their data if a decision is made in a different country. What about patient reported registries? In primary use, there is a clear case of empowerment, for e.g. xSHARE is working on a yellow button to download data from apps. Data about people is used in a different way for secondary use.

The difference with a cross-border registry is that the access to data will go through an HDAP where the coordinator of the registry is located. The EHDS does not dictate how the data is collected. The EHDS will also require datasets to be described, although it isn't clear which variables will be required yet. The bulk of the work should already be done, and it should be possible to transpose it to the EHDS. There is also tooling developed by EJPRD that allows the registry to transfer data in a DCAT compatible format.

Public consultations: <https://tehdas.eu/public-consultations/>

Session 4: Leveraging data-related opportunities (Breakout session & Discussion)

The group was split into four workshop topics and supported by a facilitator to discuss the major bottlenecks and how to tackle them:

a) Technical challenges (data acquisition, interoperability, etc.)

- There were two technical groups however, the bottle necks and issues were very similar.
- The main technical issues were data quality, SPIDER implementation and lack of standardised data.
- There was a lengthy discussion about SPIDER (pseudonymisation tool). Implementation is complicated as it must be added at each site, this also has budget implications. ERNs would like to hear more about success stories with using it. How was it done and what are the main successes?
- Apart from technical issues, there are still practical issues, so everyone needs to be part of this. If ERNs really want to be sure another ERN doesn't have their patient, it's even more of a mission! There was a suggestion to also feed this discussion back to ERDRI.
- More training and support, particularly on interoperability and SPIDER issues is needed after ERICA project stops.

b) Legal frameworks

- What is missing is a person that ERNs can turn to for expert legal and ethical advice. The group felt an overall legal advisor and/or training for ERN project managers is needed to get guidance on how ethics and data sharing works. Currently there is no point of contact to go to for advice for project managers.
- [JDRA](#) (Joint Data Registry Agreement) is a document specifically made for registries, and many found this really useful.

c) Sustainability

The obvious challenge is no dedicated funding. ERNs rely on European Commission funding, for the registries directly (e.g. to sustain things technically, for hosting, but also for staff to provide data to the registries). It would help if funding for the coordination of the ERN was more stable and permanent.

There is a perception from some (although seemingly the minority these days, as others disagree) that ERNs still shouldn't engage with pharma companies; however, this is being discussed and explored more and more, for instance through initiatives like Together4RD.

ERNs are trying to understand the implications of the European Health Data Space (EHDS) and are still waiting to hear about whether fees will be transferred to ERNs from the EHDS.

Clarification of an interface with industry is a possibility for ERNs and to have a clear framework re. What can be done so non-public funding can be explored.

Some solutions included:

- Implementation of tools like AI based tools, NLP and small language models into the registries to alleviate the burden and cost of data entry.
- Fundraising - to sustain registry. Registry and ERNS are not legal entities though.
- Industry remains a possibility of funding for providing services for them but need to make sure the access to data conforms to data access rules.
- Wherever we have several ERN registries in one place it doesn't make sense for each registry to hire someone for data entry. Could be a joint effort between registries if they are in one place.

There was support for the sharing of best practices among ERNs and scale up. 'The Registries WP' is key in those grants that have been funded by the EC for the next 4 years.

Work done under leadership in ERICA is valuable. Deliverables are confidential, however publishing some of the info and making it public would be a good way of increasing the visibility of ERN registries and what they can do.

Instead of every company setting up a registry for each new indication, it would be good to be able to make use of European RD registries. The quality is not there yet (sorry!) but perhaps there is something that can be done with what is already achieved through DARWIN and sharing costs.

The Virtual Platform in ERDERA (originating under the EJP RD) is making ERN registries visible for researchers and industry.

Cross ERN-registry studies could find patients with the same diagnosis in different registries and initiate collaborations.

Session 5: Current and Possible Future Applications of ERN Registries, including initial public-private interactions

ERN registries: improving care and supporting research

Real-world use of complement inhibitor in HUS in clinical practice:

Findings from ERKReg - Aleksandra Vujović

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C5 inhibitors (C5i) transformed the prognosis for aHUS outcomes. This is an episodic disease with high treatment costs and discontinuation strategies vary. The aim of the research was to evaluate real-world C5i use and its outcomes. ERKReg collects longitudinal data on rare kidney diseases with over 100 specialized units across 24 countries. Between 2019-2024, 979 HUS patients were enrolled in the registry and 363 aHUS patients.

The study used data from the ERKNet Registry. The dataset included diagnosis, demographics, genetics and treatments. Kidney function monitoring with annual serum creatinine updates from enrolment. Selection criteria was based on C5i treatment information and disease onset >2011 (and <2011 if treated with Eculizumab). The slides break down treatment duration by disease aetiology and by affected gene and results.

The advantages of using ERKReg included access to comprehensive, extensive structured data; Streamlined ethics with preapproved clearances easing research initiation; Cross-border collaboration; Additional data access with investigators available for quick queries; Efficient coordination via the central office; Supportive community with strong collaboration fostered through WG meetings, annual events, and shared authorship on publications.

The challenges of this approach included data inconsistencies due to duplicates and conflicting diagnoses which were addressed through investigator follow-up; Missing data (below 2%) with limited information on the initial disease severity and genetic testing; Diagnostic gap across centres and variability across units.

This was the largest real-world analysis of aHUS and iHUS since C5i was introduced. The study showed that C5i discontinuation is generally safe, with mild, manageable relapses. The study provided valuable evidence to support clinical decision-making.

A question was asked about dropouts and patients who die. Do they register this? They only had one death from their cohort and this was registered. Dropouts are the reason they use the Kaplan-Meier Analysis (KM Analysis) approach.

This work is essential as c5 inhibitors are not the most expensive of these kinds of therapies which is why there is a strong interest in discontinuing if it is not considered needed. This research provides evidence. Publication of this work has been accepted.

Research Registries: Visions as part of a cyclical approach to quality improvement - Olivia Spivack

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There are challenges with high quality healthcare for rare diseases as it can be difficult to define what care is needed and how to do it. There is also a lack of knowledge and expertise on these conditions, an absence of resources, and geographic dispersal of patients with differences between countries and hospitals and levels of undesired practice variation across Europe. There is where the ERNs come in.

The ERNICA Quality Cycle is an iterative quality improvement framework. A graphic showing the cycle is available in the slide deck.

There are five steps in the cycle: Describe desired quality of care; Promote guideline implementation; Measure quality of care; Evaluate clinical practice; Research-fill the knowledge gap.

Use Case 1: Using registry data as an 'evidence supplement' in guideline development.

Exploring innovative methodological strategies by using registry data as an evidence supplement. The ERNICA guideline on omphalocele was presented as an example. The guidelines panel was presented with raw data from the registry and asked to look at effectiveness. Twelve PICO questions were included on prenatal care, postnatal care and closure of the abdominal wall. There were 225 patients in the registry, with supplemental data from the EPSA on 7 PICO questions. The evidence supplement contributed to recommendations in 4 PICO questions.

Challenges included difficulties with data interpretation due to small samples and missing values; Missing data points; Value vs effort for panel members.

Use Case 2: Using registry data to perform implementation research and evaluate clinical practice.

Use of a clinical audit (the EPSA) as a feedback mechanism to monitor guideline implementation and its impact by alignment of EPSA core data sets and efforts to promote implementation of the registry and feedback on performance. Provision of support to centres to 'close the clinical audit cycle' and how they can follow recommendations in the future.

Use of the EPSA as way of re-auditing centre practices and associated outcomes. Aggregated EPSA data provides insight into levels of practice and outcome variation. Process evaluations with local teams explore the when, where, why and how behind successful or failed implementation.

This is useful as a way of collaboratively refining implementation strategies. It provides opportunities to capture and build on community learning experiences. If there is a lot of practice variation, this might suggest the need for a new guideline.

Supplementary measures may be needed to validate registry feedback. Practice variation might be influenced by patient preferences and characteristics.

Use case 3: Using registry data to identify research gaps.

Collaborative refinement of implementation strategies. Identifying opportunities to capture and build on community learning experiences. Identifying the need for new guidelines and revisions to existing guidelines and using registry data to identify knowledge gaps for research prioritisation.

Use Case 4: Using registry data to fill research gaps identified.

Primary use is quality improvement and secondary use for scientific research. The availability of EU data for research purposes needs to be considered. Data quality is important, so the data is ready for use. At the moment, there is a cost for extracting data. There needs to be a clear process for registry participants and how they request data. Quality improvement purposes vs other scientific research is seen differently in different countries. An internal quality team may limit the need for data requests and this needs future consideration. There is a need to balance data being collected in the right way, and being accurate and complete vs what is feasible, as there is a lot of data.

Discussion:

There was an observation that modifiable and non-modifiable factors affect outcomes and a question about whether they had considered including some of the outcome parameters they track across centres in into the monitoring system. They considered rewarding good centres with points in the system, but it was acknowledged that there are other factors affecting outcomes, such as non-compliant patients.

Strengthening research on Rare Endocrine and Bone Conditions: how complementary registry platforms support discovery and care - Ana Priego Zurita

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EuRREB (European Registries for Rare Endocrine and Bone conditions) is a combined registry for EuRRECa and EuRR-Bone. It follows a dual approach with the platforms collecting different data but complementing each other to support research.

The slides show the e-REC live case count, reporting centres and e-REC data since October 2019, as well as participation in the core registry. The e-REC collects numbers of new cases seen at HCPs. Reporters are invited to provide limited epidemiological and clinical data and reporters and patients enter longitudinal data on diagnosis, treatment and outcomes into the Core Registry. The slides give an example of VTE in Cushing Syndrome which resulted in a publication with findings from the study.

The e-REC and the Core Registry are different but complement each other to support research in rare conditions. The dual platform approach has shown its potential to identify knowledge gaps and provide a snapshot of current practices in clinical care. A clinical and research tool helps clinicians and patients understand many aspects of the disease and care. The eREC survey is a simple survey that can be customised based on admission groups and age. Id's come back and are linked to patients by centres for future studies.

A number of registries are collecting quality of care outcomes. Is this relevant for Jardin? HH commented that from an industry perspective, they lack standard of care in clinical sites across Europe. VH mentioned that from the sustainability discussion yesterday, national health authorities are providing support and funding and this should be something countries are investing in.

Caution was recommended as this is a good idea but not a one size fits all solution. Where there is a clear benefit, this is important, but for some like ITHACA, it is hard to show outcomes. Quality of care and performance can be measured more, even where outcomes cannot. Registries show where some

countries are not following guidelines, for instance that patient outcomes are worse and this is an important measure.

Performance indicators tell us something about the quality of care and this can be measured. Guideline adherence measurement shows differences between countries who are or are not following the guidelines.

Discussion:

Are all the centres in the ERNs are contributing data to the registries and are the differences in numbers between countries being measured with incentives for centres who are not contributing data? If only a subset are considered, the results and actual performance or adherence to guidelines will be impacted. There are about 50,000 in the eREC and 4,000 patients in the core registry - about 8%. Some centres that are not ERNs only put data in the core registry and not the eREC.

Monitoring the diagnostic situation of PlwRD in Europe – proposal for a cross-ERN registry use case - Holm Graessner

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Holm provided an overview of the ERDERA diagnostic research workstream and a breakdown of ERNs submitting data to ERDERA in Year 1. How to monitor what is being done in the real world setting and how to monitor the diagnostic situation of PlwRD in Europe? The aim of their use case was to collect, analyse and present aggregate data on time to diagnosis and diagnostic rate for European rare disease patients.

Almost all ERN registries collect data using the set of common data elements. Data points are also needed to define sub-groups for analysis, they are: Belonging to a specific ERN; Belonging to country (HCP); Belonging to a specific disease group; Adult vs paediatric; Patients with genetic vs without genetic diagnosis; Gender of patients; First contact with HCP. The data access and analysis proposal will be prepared February and March 2025. The pilot project to collect data from some ERNs will take place in April and May 2025 and the full project implementation with all ERNs will take place in June and July 2025. Data analysis will take place in August and September 2025.

Discussion:

There was a suggestion to make this a joint network of ERDERA and with the wider ERDERA CRN. In order to calculate time to diagnosis and age/date of diagnosis, a third variable 'date of birth' is needed. Mapping needs to be done by ERN registries.

Is disease analysis done by Orphacode? Orpha codes are there, and this exercise was done recently in the registry. There are more discrepancies between individual diseases than between disease groups. Some diseases will have small numbers, so reliability is low. Ideally, some of the analysis will be automated but quite a lot will be manual to begin with.

This is a way to expand the involvement of the ERNs however there was a suggestion that the surgically oriented ERNs would not be relevant.

Would reporting Orpha codes with age of diagnosis risk making data more identifiable? Age of onset is one of the data items collected with the worst quality due to coding issues. Patients find it hard to specify and there are antenatal diagnoses which give weird statistics.

There was a suggestion to look at whether diagnostic delay improved over time, e.g., over a five-year window using cross section and longitudinal analysis.

Will the data give enough granularity to understand why the speed of diagnosis has improved, or will this be based on speculation? The speed of diagnosis can be linked in ERDERA with technology improvement. A patient can have a clinical diagnosis before a genetic diagnosis, so a decision is needed whether to work with the clinical or genetic diagnosis. Recommendation to use the clinical diagnosis as this is already useful, followed by a recording of the genetic diagnosis.

There was a comment that care will be needed to ensure the diagnostic delay is not linked to the performance of the ERNs.

The proposal will be sent to registries for consideration. If they approve, the data transfer can be arranged.

There was a suggestion to include the patient perspective on the onset of the disease. Patients would have this information which might not be accurate otherwise. This needs further discussion.

Can data be transferred from local registries to ERDERA? Would an agreement need to be in place to do this? It is up to the ERN registry coordinators to collect the data.

Eroding barriers to ERNs working with Industry – how Together4RD is fostering collaboration - Sheela Upadhyaya

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Three pilots were launched by Together4RD in 2024, and they will continue into 2025: The RHINE Project – Rare Renal and PH International Network; Osteogenesis Imperfecta, natural history and innovative clinical trial measures; and Improving time to diagnosis for unmet patient needs in cTTP and iTTP. Together4RD want to understand the challenges and complexities around working with ERNs and industry as there are reservations that BoMS guidance remains too restrictive for ERNs wishing to work with industry. They should be encouraging research experts in ERNs and industry to advance research and support patients. The pilots will help develop an understanding about how this can work. Together4RD published an important [Position Statement](#) on multiple issues surrounding ERN and industry collaboration, which is a very useful resource to understand the status quo for this subject.

What can ERNs and industry bring to these conversations? There is a lack of understanding of the different roles they can play in these collaborations and people in industry didn't understand what ERNs are. The webinar series 'Building Bridges and understanding in rare disease research' explained this and what industry can bring to the collaboration, especially their expertise.

There has been lots of activity to engage policy makers, including MEPs to improve industry/ERN collaboration. A policy Workshop on optimising ERN-industry collaboration identified pressing issues around increased funding, clearer operational procedures and the need for tools to facilitate these collaborations. The project is currently building a Toolkit to support ERN-Industry collaboration, building on existing resources and creating new tools, where necessary. The toolkit will meet the needs of both partners and is intended to foster more collaborations. 'Collaborating for change: transforming

rare disease research and outcomes through public-private partnerships' was published in Orphanet. The report delves into a thought leader session at the European Conference of Rare Diseases in 2024.

In 2025, they will run an event in the European Parliament to highlight opportunities for public private partnerships in rare disease research and to showcase how they drive EU competitiveness and innovation in the healthcare sector. The event will show how policy makers can support this and aims to change the paradigm in the commission.

Meanwhile, Together4RD will continue to look at pilots and invite discussions from any ERNs interested in exploring the impact of rare diseases on women pre during and post pregnancy (as one of the project sponsors is interested in this topic).

Work will also continue on the toolkit, which will be published here - <https://together4rd.eu/toolkit/>

Alongside all of this, Together4RD are exploring a forum for collaboration and opportunities to help ERNs and industry find areas where they can collaborate e.g. conferences or other meetings where both are present, and side meetings can take place. They want to expand the pilot projects and look at a revised statement for the BoMS to create an environment that is open to these collaborations and to demonstrate how partnerships can expand research.

Use of ERN and other Rare Disease registries to support medicines development – Case studies:

Together4RD Pilot: RHINE project – Katarzyna Mosiewicz

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The goal of this pilot is to unlock the potential of data in Rare Renal by data harmonisation and application of a robust interoperability model. The specific objective of this pilot is to improve pathways in care in Primary Hyperoxaluria (PH)/Rare kidney disorders, including diagnosis and referral pathways. Over a 12–15-month timeframe, the pilot will build 'evidence-based' care pathways in PH whilst looking at other rare kidney stone diseases. The team will perform educational and knowledge dissemination activities and perform KPI testing to evaluate the effectiveness over time of educational initiatives and changes in clinical practice.

The key stakeholders here are ERKNet (ERN), Oxal/Europe, Patient Organisations and Novo Nordisk. The aim is to identify bottlenecks and define and co-create initiatives and to see what can be learned from registry data, and to bring expertise, not just funding, to ERN collaborations. Resolving issues with linking pre-existing or separate disease specific registries is very important.

The research started with mapping of aggregate data from ERKNet and OxalEurope and it was important to identify duplicate patients at this stage to avoid skewing the data in this rare condition. The next steps were to align variables, combine follow up data, merge and remove doubles, followed by analyses. Missing data in both registries was queried before moving on to the second analyses to understand clinical care pathways. Patient representatives from each disease have already been engaged in one session and the goal is to involve them in actively reviewing research protocols, identifying unmet needs, enhancing patient information and co-developing the patient journeys. Collecting patient reported outcomes may be important in the future.

The project wants to transform the clinical care pathway holistically from diagnosis to early intervention and improve patient outcomes by having a common goal.

Discussion:

There was a comment that this is a one-off activity so how it would it make future integration with registries easier? This is a pilot project so is looking at how to map data decisions in the best way and complimenting data items collected by OxalEurope. Sites that contributed to both registries are mostly complementary. They now have requests from other registries who would like to align with ERKNet. They also have very active feedback from the group of patients.

Models of industry collaboration applied by ERKReg – Franz Schaefer

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ERKReg is an advanced registry with many patients. It is based on a modular concept with a core registry and modular sub-registries on specific diseases/disease groups. The registry started in 2018 and now has 28,000 rare kidney disease patients which means they have sizable cohorts for analysis.

Data access requests go through the data access committee, and they have had requests from industry for information on certain diseases.

There are three models for interactions with industry. The brokerage function is followed when a company is planning to run a clinical trial and wants to find patients for eligibility criteria. They inform the local investigator that a trial is available for the patient, and they talk to the patient and ask if they are interested. If they are, they provide the company with the contact information for the investigator. This has been successful, with two trials to date, and more in the contracting phase.

The second way they collaborate with industry is to receive requests for data access. After the request has been received, the statistician checks to see if the questions are feasible to answer. The Board approves the data access request, and the company is provided with a report containing aggregated data. Only patients who have consented to sharing their data with commercial partners (about 85-90%) are included. To date, 6 analyses of this kind have been completed, and a publication is in preparation. Academic researchers can use this data once it's been published and is in the public space.

The third way is to develop disease-specific sub-registries with industry. They co-create data dictionaries according to the industry partner's needs. It is then validated by the ERKNet Board and is promoted online. Data fields can be retrospectively completed. Participation in sub registries is voluntary, and data used by the sponsors is always provided on a non-exclusive basis. They receive some funding for this work from the companies which is used to support the sites - fees on a per patient basis using an amendment to the collaboration agreements. Three sub registries have been successfully launched in this way: each one sponsored by more than one sponsor which is cheaper for the companies.

In the future they want to transform sub registries to a granularity of data collection that would meet regulatory requirements. This would mean long term funding and support for these registries. PMS would mean different data collection, including data they don't collect at the moment, and quality issues and considerations. Regulatory grade data collection is another level from regular registries.

Discussion:

In response to a question about foundation conditional grants from industry, Franz responded that this is a fourth mechanism and a model that was applied to patient associations who receive commercial and patient funding. Franz has a contract with them to run a registry, and they receive funds from industry and pay based on this contract. This means ERKReg doesn't have to pay overhead fees to the hospital administration as they don't charge overheads to charity organisations.

In response to a question about whether co-created data dictionaries reach a point at which they are complete, Franz Schaefer responded that there are many different disease types, and this is the case for some of them. Others have a lot of different, very specific data items.

It takes a lot of work to contribute the data. Some sites are very interested and engaged and have dedicated research nurses in place for additional data collection – around 20-25 sites. Another 40-50 sites have lower levels of commitment, and they get less responses from patients.

A question was asked whether all registries are able to carry out consent to identify patients who do not want to be involved, or is there a special form? The majority of registries will use the consent form; however, the old consent form does not include these data requests, so they are trying to re-consent patients which is a lot of work. So long as it is clear that there is an independent review, hospitals are fine with these requests. Their boards approve these requests which makes them ERN or ERN registry activities.

Establishing Public-Private Collaborations centred on the TREAT-NMD registries – Rebecca Leary

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The TREAT-NMD global registries network works with industry to provide regulatory grade data for drug development. The registry network has 69 member registries in 42 countries with almost 90,000 neuromuscular patients globally, mostly with a genetic diagnosis. The mission is to create a sustainable, federated global network of registries. Most of the registries have a mixed model - national, international and regional. Data can be patient reported – with or without clinician verification, clinician reported, or a combination of patient and clinician reported.

Registries within the TREAT-NMD Global Registry Network collect data using agreed datasets. The specification of these is published online, and includes lists of data items, data dictionary, and recommended data collection questions. Data sets were set for trial readiness, and this has developed into post marketing surveillance and natural history studies as more neuromuscular drugs become available. The network also supports new registries via the centralised Global Registries Platform. Wherever the data comes from, it is stored centrally in a data warehouse for analysis.

Case studies include natural history studies, post-authorisation studies, contextualising clinical trials and real-world efficacy studies. Challenges include infrastructure, process and quality requirements and the high quality of required data. The strength of the network is that it is able to answer complex research questions. The EMA offers qualification of patient registries and TREAT-NMD requested scientific advice on qualification, covering all aspects of network data collected, infrastructure etc. As a result of this advice, a Letter of Support was issued by EMA in late 2022. This was a challenging, in-depth process but may be something to aspire to.

Project PaLaDIn was also presented. PaLaDIn is a 4-year, Horizon Europe Innovative Health Initiative (IHI) project worth €21.4M. PaLaDIn will develop and implement an innovative data collection platform (the Interactium) to accelerate the development of effective treatments and patient care, enhance healthcare decision-making and improve patient outcomes.

Discussion:

In response to a question about how a global registry network manages data quality, Becca responded that not all data from all registries is at the right level for post-marketing surveillance. There is a separate model for quality data that usually comes from clinicians. There are also inbuilt tools to identify obvious errors.

A question was asked about how much overlap there is between data points and Phase IV registry. The network has a core dataset. If a registry collects additional data items, it is elevated to a different level, so this is dependent on an expanded dataset rather than a different registry.

Becca commented that she is not involved in the finances, in response to a question about multi-company support for core funding for the central platform, but understands it is still funded on a project-by-project basis.

The Experiences of the European Cystic Fibrosis Registry – Lutz Nährlich

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In 2003, the European Cystic Fibrosis Society started consenting patients with Cystic Fibrosis and agreed inclusion criteria. 42 countries contributed data (across WHO Europe) and 56,000 patients reported to them. Aim for over 80% coverage as with rare disease, every patient counts. The main challenges are commitment, governance, diversity/languages and successful cooperations. It is important to get people to step in and feel involved in order to feel seen. The advantage of joining ECFSPR/ECFS is visibility on an international level.

From a governance perspective, everything is seen as a research goal. Every country is informed about every research request and can opt out. It is important to include everyone on publications and to give due credit to all sites. They want to have informed consent from patients advocating for their rights and need to have transparency about finances and industry collaboration. It is important to understand the reimbursement process in different countries, so they have 18 national registries with their own infrastructures and data collection, but they all upload a harmonised dataset. They have a data collection platform (ESCFSPR Tracker used by 24 countries) that serves as a data warehouse.

Data needs to be of high quality for research. They have a data dictionary and data entry/upload checks and data validation. They ask centres about their challenges and have dialogue at the centre level. There is a high level of data completeness and of correct data. Achievements include epidemiologic overview, research output and pharmacovigilance. Data for pharmacovigilance must be fit for purpose; it is important to deliver what was promised and to keep a balance between being a research registry and a service provider.

The question of how ERN can efficiently engage with other existing registries was raised.

In response to a question about whether industry comes on board *because* there is a good registry, or *because* the high-quality registries are only in areas where there a drug is available, and therefore there is pharma interest, Lutz suggested that industry comes on board when there is a good registry.

There was a suggestion that there needs to be investment in trial readiness for ERN registries. In response to a question about whether representativeness is based on the number of patients or the coverage, Lutz commented that coverage is important.

Using registry data for post-marketing-surveillance: insights from the UK SMA experience – Elena Karkkainen

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Post-marketing surveillance is the continuous monitoring of a treatment for safety and effectiveness. Adult SMA reach is a multi-centre longitudinal observational data collection initiative. It tracks real world outcomes for SMA patients in collaboration with paediatric and patient reported registries in the UK. Stakeholders are pharmaceutical companies, NHS England, Researchers and Regulators.

The database was launched in October 2022 with 9 sites. There are currently 18 active sites.

Case Study 1 – Regulatory approval: Aim to provide real-world evidence on effectiveness and safety OR cost effectiveness? The challenges included lack of data and infrastructure to collect data nationally; the dataset, SAP and aim were not pre-defined when the project was first launched; RWD is not trial data and is collected in real-world settings and the final SAP and data collection processes were not real-world applicable. Several learnings came from the case study, including the need for a methodological approach to project development and early engagement from all stakeholders, taking into account real-world considerations and addressing site/clinical constraints and capacity. The main learning from this case study was for automated data curation and processing of RWD for analysis. The case study supported regulatory decision to approve and fund the treatment with high quality real-world data.

Case Study 2 – Research: Aim to provide high quality real-world data for new initiatives, projects, basic research, care advancement and influence future research direction. The challenges included the fact that manual work is cumbersome, time-consuming and prone to human error and that real-world data is not trial data. A data model was used to validate data by detecting missing and unknown data and identifying inconsistencies. The outcomes from this case study were an automated and efficient data curation process; identification of common issues within rare disease and RWD; providing high-quality real-world data for research initiatives.

Case Study 3 – Clinicians and patients: The main challenges with this case study were the patient to clinical staff ratio, the amount of manual work involved and long and frequent assessments. The main outcomes were giving back to patients and clinical team, 12 monthly visits and providing guidance of clinical visit assessment focus.

Conclusions for the future focus for the UK SMA registry include: data validation at data entry; the importance of collaborations and data sharing; use of established networks for kick-off training and sub studies; the importance of learning from the data itself; use of RWD for standardising care management nationally; enabling tailored treatment strategies and tracking long-term outcomes.

Discussion:

There was a comment that there were 720 variables collected and 1700 visits – that is a lot of variables collected per visit. Not all the data collected was mandatory and there is a need to evaluate what needs to be collected in the future.

Another question asked how long it took to get the data. Elena responded that once they had decided on the data items and understood needs, it was a maximum of 2 months.

Session 6: Considerations for using ERN registries to generate regulatory-grade real-world evidence

RWD/RWE for (Regulatory) Decision making - industry perspective - Heidrun Hildebrand

Supported by Kristina An Haack, Sanofi & Kiliانا Suzart-Woischnik, Bayer Pharmaceuticals

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Heidrun Hildebrand, Bayer Pharmaceuticals, presented the Real World Data (RWD) definition taken from the FDA (the framework of 2018). Based on this definition, RWD are data relating to patient health status and/or the delivery of healthcare that is routinely collected from a variety of sources, including product and disease registries. The presentation demonstrated the generation of Real World Evidence (RWE) for RWD in clinical trials.

Where RWD are currently used to support regulatory decision making:

- Internal decision making, for example for understanding Natural History or the standard of care.
- Selecting the right population.
- Development of paediatric investigation plans.
- Study planning and design.

All of this type of information originates from registries, claims data or electronic health records.

Heidrun showed how aggregated information, and patient level information can be obtained from electronic health records and registries to support new indications or label changes to post approval studies. For example, long-term safety follow-up in past studies, or drug utilization studies.

Up to date patient information can also be used to support today's market authorisation applications for new indications. However, the quality of the RWD are important for application in the regulatory decision-making process. For example, it is essential to define the governance of the registries, the data dictionaries that are in place, the matching population, the relevance of data registries, the consistency and reliability of the data etc.

Heidrun then presented some use cases.

The objective of one study was to evaluate the mathematical relation between biomarkers and clinical outcomes in the given population and to quantify the influence of the age and potentially other co-factors in this relationship. It also studied whether the relationship in paediatric patients can compare to the respective relationship for adult patients. In this use case the data sources were the paediatric cardiomyopathy registry and the IBM Watson database. The data included for the evaluation were demography, baseline characteristics, medication, blood data and clinical outcomes. Final outcomes: A relationship between biomarker and the clinical outcome could be established and is currently implemented in an ongoing study.

A use case was presented based on a post authorisation safety study. The objective was to evaluate the trend in drug utilisation patterns in the UK of a prefilled syringe plus a paediatric dosing device in the raw patient population. It summarised the clinical characteristics of the patients. In this case the

data source was the UK national neonatal research database. The data included for evaluation were demography, gestational age, birth weight, Apgar comorbidity etc. The outcome of this study was to inform the decision on whether the number of preterm infants with ROP exposed to the Eylea prefilled syringe + PDD is sufficient to proceed with a court study to investigate the long-term safety.

Another use case looked at support for full approval of a rare disease indication. The objective was to complement evidence from registrational clinical trials about clinical effectiveness. The data source was the sponsored Fabry registry and the international epidemiologic study of the Natural History of Fabry disease. The data annualised eGFR slope over 5 years, and the composite event variable defined as the first post baseline occurrence of different events. The outcome of this study was a substantially lower rate of eGFR decline in adult patients with FD receiving agalsidase beta than that in matched untreated patients, as reported in the US Prescribing Information. The RWE was used in the supplemental biologics license application to the Food and Drug Administration to support full approval of agalsidase beta.

Methodological and practical considerations around the use of patient registries for regulatory purposes – Carla Jonker

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Carla Jonker from the data analytics and methods task force of the RWE work team of the EMA presented on using registries for regulatory purposes. She talked about the added value of patient registries and about the EMA patient registry initiative.

Classic randomised controlled clinical trials are the gold standard to generate primary safety and efficacy of medicinal products, but they have limitations and some challenges. The RWD coming from hospital data registries, claims databases, surveys electronic health records etc., may complement evidence generated pre- and post-authorisation. For example, during the trial preparation (patients recruitment, randomized allocation, sample size calculation, and endpoint identification), in the clinical context (Natural History and course of disease), the patterns of medicines authorisation, in the risk categorisation in the evaluation of medicine long term efficacy and safety profile and in the assessment of RMM effectiveness.

The EMA patient registries initiatives aim to optimise and facilitate the use of existing disease registries and to promote dialogue between the stakeholders and to provide guidance for use of registries for regulatory purposes. The aim is to have more comprehensive flexible and sustainable resources to understand barriers and opportunities of using disease registries and to clarify methodological concepts and requirements.

One of the EMA's essential documents is the [guideline on registry based studies](#) that includes recommendations on key methodological and operational aspects of registry-based studies such as the relevant legal basis and the regulatory requirements.

The importance of registry-based studies has evidence in the rare disease context which are faced with small patient populations, limited knowledge on disease natural history, and a lot of heterogeneity of disease phenotype/genotype or disease progression. There is a long time span to observe the therapeutic benefit in a slow progressive disease and also for ethical considerations. All these points result in difficulties in recruitment, the identification of relevant outcome measures, and there is also

a threshold of meaningful evidence. This impacts on traditional approaches of extrapolation between paediatric/adults and interpretation of clean traditional clinical outcomes.

In the context of rare diseases, randomised clinical trials are not always “fit for purpose” to establish sufficient evidence on safety and efficacy. There is a need to define appropriate approaches to using external data sets as comparators. In this context, the single arm trial designs may be considered (e.g. diseases with high unmet needs and rapid progression, disease modifying therapies, and the lack of acceptability of placebo control arms).

When planning to conduct a registry-based study, the following steps were outlined. First, identify the research questions (what do you want to study?) Second, perform a landscape analysis (EMA real world catalogues). Third, carry out a feasibility assessment evaluation of the fitness for purpose of the registry (are the existing registries relevant?).

It is essential to answer these questions: Whether the data set captures key data elements to address a research question in a reliable, coherent and timely way; Whether the number of patients and follow up times are sufficient to demonstrate the impact of the intervention/determinants under investigation; Early dialogue with all relevant stakeholders is important; HMA-EMA Data Quality Framework; REQuest Tool, Structured Process to Identify Fit-for-Purpose Study Design and Data (SPIFD) framework.

The feasibility analysis is to be performed by the MAA/MAH or the research organisation initiating the registry-based study in collaboration with registry holders to facilitate the discussion with regulators and other parties.

It can help to answer essential questions on the suitability of using the infrastructure of the registry for a specific registry-based study. If there are any doubts, another study design could be a better choice.

The following questions should be answered: Is the governance model in place appropriate? Is the registry population appropriately representative? Are the requirements for additional informed consent feasible? Is the primary data collection feasible? Are the collected data sufficient for the purpose of this study? Is the time lag for the reliability of the data suitable? Are the data of demonstrated quality?

The RWD catalogue of sources is available at <https://catalogues.ema.europa.eu/>

The data catalogue defines the data source, the study, the execution, and the network. The catalogue is useful to:

- Enhance discoverability and evaluation of data sources and studies -> facilitating the use of RWD sources, ultimately supporting evidence-based regulatory decision-making.
- Link RWD sources and studies which can support study design, protocol evaluation, and results interpretation.
- Facilitate collaboration and research.
- Promote transparency in observational research and reduce publication bias by making publicly available metadata on non-interventional studies.
- Promote good practices aligning with 'FAIR' data principles for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable data.
- Respond to the DARWIN EU open call to become a DARWIN data partner via the Catalogues.

- Free access via the Catalogues webpage, hosted on EMA public website

In 2023 the European medicine agency released the data quality framework for EU medicines regulation. This document provides general information for describing, characterising and assessing data qualities for decision making.

Data Quality Framework - Example of metrics

Dimension	Metric category	Example metrics	Example
Reliability	Plausibility checks	% of records where logical constraints between values is in line with expectations	For X% of records, discharge date happens before admission date
	Checks on dataset descriptors	% of variables/datasets that are based on imputation or derivation	End of treatment date is derived for X% of patients from treatment start date and treatment cycle length
Extensiveness	Comparison to other datasets	Relative percentage of records for which a variable is missing with respect to a trusted source of knowledge	X% of patients with missing date of diagnosis in a diabetes database, compared to a National and institutionally validated diabetes registry
Coherence	Conformance check	For relevant variables, % of records where data values conform to allowable values or ranges	X% of records have sex with one of the 3 allowable values "M", "F", or "U".
Timeliness	Objective dataset assessment	Average time of updates in a database	Timestamps indicate patient records are updated on average every 3 months (after hospital visit)

Classified as public by the European Medicines Agency

It is in this context that the EMA big data initiatives were developed as part of the EU's current framework to unlock value, enable the use of RWD, and facilitate integration into regulatory decision making.

One example is the DARWIN EU data analysis and the real-world interrogation network. DARWIN EU is a federated network of data, expertise and services that supports better decision-making throughout the product lifecycle by generating valid and reliable evidence from real-world healthcare data.

In conclusion:

- Registry data (RWD) are valuable and have a crucial role in bridging the gap between clinical research and practice.
- Various initiatives exist to enable and leverage their use (Big Data, Patient Registry initiatives).
- Various guidance documents/tools exist to help build a patient registry and assess its relevance for research (guideline on RBS, DQF, RWD catalogues etc...).
- Dialogue with future users at an early stage and throughout lifecycle of medicines (e.g., EMA interaction pathways).
- Opportunities for collaboration on evidence generation (e.g., DARWIN EU)

Breakout Session: Assessing current aspirations and challenges to using ERN registries to support drug development, and identifying solutions

The groups discussed what kinds of activities ERN registries are able to perform at present, and assessed their longer-term plans (or otherwise) to evolve these registries to support activities like clinical trial design and delivery, and to support post-marketing studies. The exercise sought to better understand what stakeholders felt would hamper ERNs in efforts to make their registries more powerful and more able to serve a range of purposes.

Not every registry envisages serving all of the 7 purposes suggested in the exercise.

The main goals either *already* being pursued by responding registries, or else anticipated within less than 3 years, were

- **generating new insights and knowledge** (only 1 saw this as something only coming to fruition outside of the next 3 years)
- **benchmarking care** (most saw this becoming possible in less than 3 years)
- **supporting recruitment for clinical research** (most saw this becoming possible in less than 3 years)

In terms of driving care improvements, ambitions and expectations were a little divided – of 13 who responded to this one, 7 anticipating this becoming a reality for the registries within less than 3 years (with 4 already able to do this), whereas the other 6 felt this would take longer.

The picture was also quite mixed, when it came to the possibility of ERN registries **supporting clinical trials feasibility assessments**: of the 12 who responded here, half felt this was either already possible, or else would be within 3 years, whereas the other 6 felt this would take longer than 3 years (with 4 i.e. a third, estimating this would take at least 5 years to implement, if indeed it ever comes to pass.)

When it comes to **supporting adaptive or innovative methodologies for trial design**, and **providing RWE to support post authorisation studies**, the most popular answers were '>5 years or not sure', with only 1 registry reporting an ability to do these things at present, in 2025.

Activity	Doing already/ in 2025	<3 years	3-5 years	>5 years or don't know
Supporting recruitment for clinical research	4	3	2	2
Supporting adaptive or innovative methodologies for trial design	1	2	2	4
Providing RWE to support post authorisation studies	1	3	2	3
Generating new insights and knowledge	3	6	1	0
Benchmarking care	2	6	2	1
Driving care improvements	4	3	5	1
Supporting clinical trials feasibility assessments	3	3	2	4

The groups provided some important feedback about why these saw some of these activities as sitting relatively far in the future, highlighting enablers and barriers.

Feedback from Group 1

- Discussion about how much ERNs and their registries really talk about strengths and aspirations internally. Do most registries have longer-term plans and strategies for how they'd like to evolve their registries? Is one of the cross-RD projects e.g. ERDERA, JARDIN, or the ERN Coordinators' Group, actually fostering discussions about this?
- The main blocks to ERN registries evolving to do more are quite fundamental: data entry challenges and just getting the basics right – getting the registries working and showing what they can do.
- Although we say this often, the importance cannot be underestimated - each ERN is very different! And this applies to their registries too. It seems they all have different goals and aspirations right now.

Barriers:

- All ERNs have pre-existing or parallel disease registries which contain the rich disease-oriented data and there is not an easy way to connect these and link that data, which would be needed for regulatory purposes.
- Would not want to unnecessarily duplicate work.
- No Incentive sometimes to move into these directions! If the space is not taken, someone should do it. A drug in the pipeline can be incentive to a registry serving these sorts of trial readiness and pharmacovigilance purposes
- For some, the main focus of ERNs was on care and should remain that way. Dedicated limited resources for research purposes may mean choices have to be made to avoid losing the care potential. Others also remarked that the boundary between care and research is blurred so it is important to do both – without losing the USP of cross-European care structures.
- Moving into new registry directions isn't so easy (with the 5-year grant funding).
- Data quality is key and there is not a natural given that data quality is good.
- NB the absence of the enablers below can be viewed as a barrier!

Enablers:

- Dedicated staff to go around to sites to support data entry.
- Sustainable funding! It is enough to do all the things you want without losing the care.
- Overarching ERN registry structure (no ERICA, the ERN Coordinators WG) to drive these issues and debates, to share good practices.
- The potential for widely sharing of experiences and good practices across ERNs.
- Ability to see how others have moved ahead, including best practices on practical things, but also 'every other level' – e.g. going into Industry collaborations.
- Mentality to fill the gaps. If a space is very busy, and not everyone plays ball together, how can you find constructive ways to meet unmet needs.

Feedback from Group 2

Barriers:

- Quality signals are missing, which is a barrier. As soon as we go into the regulatory or clinical trials field, we need to think that we don't have things like source data verification. If we have the desire, we still need funding to do these things, as we are research-oriented hospitals.
- Gathering observational data, not acting on study protocols so the datasets are going to be skewed by clinical practice and, moreover, clinical practice AT a particular hospital.
- Clinical trial-related activities would need a level of data completeness that most ERN registries do not have.
- ERNs don't have the strength of legal entities, would have to work as a consortium of hospitals, and individual hospitals would need to make the contracts, which can be a burden for some.

Feedback from Group 3

Barriers and Enablers:

- Identification of patients for clinical trials.
- Lack of, or inappropriate, informed consent for ERN registries to serve some of these purposes.
- ERN registries could provide data to serve as a control arm in clinical trials - this would be helped by having really comprehensive data collections from frequent patient visits, but it needs to be high-quality data. There would need to be clear guidelines for data collection. Perhaps registry holders should already start to think now about how to make data collection ready for regulatory purposes.
- Complexity of the regulatory requirements for datasets to be accepted for external controls is a barrier – it is difficult to understand exactly what regulators will accept as evidence.
- Thinking specifically about RWD to support post-marketing studies - the most important issue is to have appropriate funding. Fulfilling these kinds of regulatory purposes is quite a burden - e.g. it may overburden investigators as they would need to report adverse events at short notice. It is important to engage in such studies, but most ERNs are not ready for that yet.
- The group also talked about the possibility of registry cohorts training AI models to come up with virtual cohorts/patients that could be used to complement real cohorts (synthetic data and twinning of the populations).
- It would be important to have an operating registry but also then have data easily available. Preliminary data could perhaps be publicly available on a website, via a dashboard, so companies know how many patients each registry has and what kind of diagnoses, etc. This would be a big enabler for some of these types of activity.

Conclusions and agreed actions

The following actions were proposed in the final section of the workshop:

1. Create a workshop report (the current document) with links to the slide presentations and consider how this report might be further developed into a peer-reviewed publication. The paper could focus specifically on:

- The status quo for ERN registries.
- Challenges and barriers to successful ERN registry operations.
- ERN aspirations for future use of these registries.

In addition to these outputs, a number of specific actions were suggested.

2. There was a general consensus that specific taskforces or similar should be set-up to advance certain actions under the soon-to-be-reformulated ERN Coordinators' Group Working Group on Research (ERN CG). One such focus could be on KPIs. Another focus could be a taskforce on tangible use cases. Some of these suggestions could potentially be a use case for the ERDERA data services hub. An AI working group has been proposed under the ERN CG by Maurizio Scarpa. There was also a proposal for that the ERN CG and any registry-related taskforces be connected to the registry project managers group, which meets remotely, once per month.

3. It is important to collect questions on the EHDS and what it means for registries, especially based on the presentation from David Asturiol. ERN registry teams need information quite urgently, on the following:

- What will be the full impact and ramifications of the EHDS on registries? More information about what ERN registries will need to do.
- How registries might change as a result of the EHDS.
- How current procedures for data access committees etc will still work (or not) under the EHDS.
- Whether the ERDRI tools they have been contributing to will serve as the repository mentioned in the presentation, or whether the VP can do this role, or something else. How will it work?
- How will fees for data access/data processing work?

Clearer information is needed about what the EHDS will BRING, and what people see as the threats/disadvantages. As a result of this discussion, the EC will arrange such a workshop for the ERN registries which may address outstanding questions.

4. Share the registry status quo, based on Jose Ramírez-García's data on Day 1, and publish some vignettes to showcase this potential. This could come via the publication in point 1. Some deliverables of ERICA may be confidential, but it may be possible to do more with these outputs. It would help to advertise these achievements to national policymakers, Industry, etc., and show them the different sorts of value of these resources). There was also a suggestion to use this workshop report to generate the second article in the new ERN publication series (after the initial publication highlighting *all* ERN activities). There may be other opportunities, such as a registry webinar series.

5. Look into organising a 'best practice presentation' workshop for the registries.

6. Have a central website where all the ERN registries could be represented to show what they do and where to find them. Orphanet has this data, but it is currently not all on one page. ERICA has created this resource so this action may not be needed, unless there was a plan to create a live, dashboard.
7. Arrange a virtual session/workshop specifically around SPIDER, looking at how people are using it and what it brings. This could potentially be one of the taskforces or use cases under the ERDERA data services hub.
8. Make short clear summaries of what work in ERDERA and JARDIN and others (e.g. c4c, c4c-S, Together4RD, eHealth projects Henrique Martins mentioned and our ERN X-Net) – are planning to do with regards to ERN registries. Many don't know the full picture.
9. Find a home for future workshops, focused on some of the hot topics brought together in this busy workshop. Can we envisage a workshop on the different approaches/status quo, and suggested good practices and solutions, to meaningfully bring-in patient data/PROMs data to these ERN registries? Could ERN registries be somehow involved in DARWIN EU (launched by EMA to integrate real-world data into the regulatory decision-making process)? In the absence of funding for in-person workshops, perhaps the taskforces mentioned in the first point could take charge of this.
10. Make it clear if/how ERN registries can use some of these tools presented e.g. SAMS, can be applied to their registry and what they can bring (e.g. are they more about diagnostics, more about standardised and interoperable data?) Besides sharing the slides in this report, these resources could be further presented and demonstrated at meetings of the new Taskforces mentioned above, or in the registry project managers group. Dedicated webinars could follow, with an emphasis on how to practically implement.
11. Explore further how the RD and paediatric space is working with the more mainstream EHDS projects and structures. E.g. Henrique Martins highlighted the eHNetwork guideline inclusion of Orphacode in the Patient Summary, that we worked on a few years ago, and the inclusion of a paediatric clinical research focus in X-Share. These are good ways forward, but we should really put the ERN X-Net into action here.

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